

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

LRP1

(LDL receptor related protein 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	4035 / Q07954
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.49 (rank #1975, 92.1th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.49 out of 5 (rank #1975, 92.1th percentile). The individual score components include 1.53 of 3 for genetics, and 1.96 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of both LRP1 protein and RNA is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. LRP1 is annotated to GO terms from 10 different biodomain, primarily to terms from the Endolysosome, Lipid Metabolism, and APP Metabolism biological domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.49	1975	92.09	1.533	1.957

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence

measures of expression. The expression of LRP1 is confidently detected in most cell types within this dataset, with the highest expression detected in vascular and leptomeningeal cells (VLMC), microglia, and oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC).

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

LRP1 is involved in regulating both amyloid and tau pathology associated with AD pathogenesis. The extracellular domain, as discussed below, binds not only amyloid and tau, but also ApoE alleles—with stronger associations demonstrated for ApoE2/3 than ApoE4(1-6). The complex set of LRP1 associations may have broad impacts on neuronal physiology, as well as innate immune function, both of which are central to AD pathogenesis. The goal of this project is to provide resources to investigate the role of LRP1 in AD more exhaustively through the characterization and testing of specific antibodies, development of purified protein, and the development of a set of bioinformatics resources for LRP1.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

LDL receptor related protein 1 (LRP1) is a member of the LDL Receptor (LDLR) gene family which includes LDLR, LRP1B, LRP2, VLDLR, apoER2, SorLA and LRP5/6. LRP1 is a complex gene with 89 exons that encode both the 85 kDa single pass transmembrane protein and the associated 515 kDa extracellular moiety (UniProt, UCSD Genome Browser Card) that associates with multiple factors including amyloid, APOE, and tau (1-6). The extracellular moiety is furin cleaved from the holoprotein and remains non-covalently associated with the 85 kDa membrane spanning fragment (1). There are four independent ligand binding domains within the extracellular region with variable numbers of cysteine rich complement type repeats. The 85 kDa membrane spanning portion of LRP1 contains concatenated EGF repeats within the extracellular region, a transmembrane domain, that, like APP, is cleaved by alpha-, beta- and the heterotetrameric gamma-secretase complex, releasing the intracellular domain (1, 7, 8). The intracellular portion of LRP1 contains two NPTY motifs, like the NPTY motif in APP, which allow it to complex with APBB1 and Kat5 (9). The similarity in processing pathways between LRP1 and APP is likely one mechanism by which LRP1 can regulate amyloid levels, by competing with APP for proteolytic processing(8).

The amyloid peptide also binds directly to LRP1, and LRP1 is implicated in amyloid clearance in multiple cell types, including astrocytes, microglia and endothelial cells (1). The regulation of amyloid levels by LRP1 may occur in ApoE independent and dependent mechanisms, as studies show that amyloid-ApoE complexes (specifically with ApoE2/3, but not ApoE4) bind the extracellular fragment of LRP1 (1, 10). This suggests that LRP1 may have differential effects upon neuronal viability depending on the ApoE allele composition present, which is reported in several studies and reviews (10-14). Further, the interaction between ApoE and cholesterol lipids, strongly implicates LRP1 in cholesterol trafficking (1). The presence of an endocytosis motif in the intracellular domain of LRP1, allows it to be rapidly internalized into cells for immediate degradation. Additionally, LRP1 is heavily expressed in the liver, and may be responsible for removing amyloid species from blood and mediating their degradation. One additional mechanism exists for LRP-mediated regulation of amyloid via the association of amyloid with the soluble ectodomain of LRP1, complexing amyloid in blood or CSF, promoting its sequestration and degradation. Additionally, LRP1 plays a signalling role in neurons that may facilitate neuronal homeostasis, as LRP1 over-expression in neuronal cultures precipitates elevated levels of synapse formation, an effect that may be mediated by ApoE in an isoform dependent manner (ApoE2/3 promoting synapse formation, ApoE4 not) (1). Similar ApoE isoform dependent effects have been observed in cognitive neuroimaging studies, demonstrating an interaction between LRP1 polymorphisms and ApoE4 allelic presence in MMSE scores (15). In addition to neurons, many studies find a role for LRP1 in the regulation of innate immune response, both in macrophages and

microglial cellular lineages (16, 17). TREAT-AD identified LRP1 as a strong scoring component of a module identified within deep-proteomic studies that correlated with an increase in pathology and a decrease in cognitive score (18), module 42 (M42), which also contains APP and APOE as top drivers. While LRP biology is multifaceted and complex, it remains an interesting potential therapeutic venue to explore in the treatment of AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for LRP1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for LRP1 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

Complete report: [LRP1 antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

1. LRP1A-c004: Human LRP1 (E20-E172). Contains a N-terminal 6His and C-terminal AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Sf9 cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of LRP1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

Additional Information

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. **LRP1A-c004**: Human LRP1 (E20-E172). Contains a N-terminal 6His and C-terminal AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Sf9 cells.

Construct ID	LRP1A-c004
Parental vector	pFB-Sec-Bio5
Tag	N-terminal 6-His-TEV Tag, C-terminal AviTag
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	23932.7 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1}cm^{-1}$)	18450
Protein sequence (with tag)	MVSAIVLYVLLAAAAHSAFAAAMGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSM AIDAPKTCSPKQFA CRDQITCISKGWRC DGERDCPDGSDEAPEICPQSKAQRCPNEHNLGTELCVPMSRLCN GVQDCMDGSDGPHCRELQGNCSRLGCQHHCVPTLDGPTCYCNSSFQLQADGKTCKDFD ECSVYGTCSQLCTNTDGSFISSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
Size Exclusion Chromatography: LRP1A-c004 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: LRP1A-c004 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	1 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Insect:</i> SF9 cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	Sf900-II SFM Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Virus Generation	For transposition, transform construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain DH10Bac. Plate on LB-agar plates containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml), tetracycline (10 µg/ml), IPTG (40 µg/ml) and bluogal (300 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml) and tetracycline (10 µg/ml) with a single

	colony and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Perform MiniPrep (Millipore) according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 1 volume of isopropanol to precipitate the bacmid DNA. Spin (13000g, 20 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend bacmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transfect Sf9 cells at a density of 2×10^6 cells/ml. 2. Just before infection, add 2% FBS to the cells. 3. Infect the cells with 120 μl of P0 Baculovirus stock and incubate at 27°C, with shaking at 450 rpm in a Glas-Col shaker for 66-72 h and harvest P1 baculovirus. 4. Pellet the cells by centrifugation at 1500 x g for 20 min and harvest the supernatant Repeat steps 2 and 3, then infect the cells with 120 μl of P1 baculovirus stock and incubate at 27°C, with shaking at 450 rpm in a Glas-Col shaker for 66-72 Pellet the cells by centrifugation at 900 x g for 30 min for purification.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thaw pellet and resuspend to 40mL LB. 2. Sonicate at amplitude 35%, pulse 5s on/ 10s off, 20 minutes. 3. Centrifuge at 22,000g 30 mins. Decant cleared supernatant. 4. Add 3ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads and bind for 1h with rotation at 4°C. 5. Spin at 700g for 5 mins and decant the supernatant. 6. Spin beads/lysate slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 7. Wash column with 25 ml W25. 8. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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